

HIGH TEMPERATURE THERMAL EXPLOSIVE SYNTHESIS OF NICKEL/NICKEL ALUMINIDE MULTILAYER COMPOSITES

Huabin Wnag, Jie-Cai Han and Shanyi Du

Center for Composite Materials, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin, China

SUMMARY: Full density nickel-nickel aluminide multilayer composites were successfully fabricated by thermal explosive synthesis of metal foil laminations at 620°C for 1h under 1 MPa pressure and post-treatment for 4 hours at 750 °C, 950 °C and 1150 °C under 5 MPa pressure in vacuum, respectively. The ductile nickel layers in composites can significantly improve room temperature toughness by bridging mechanism of multiple cracks. For post treatment at 750 °C and 950 °C, the composites are easy to delaminate at low tensile stress level because of the poor-bonded interface and the existence of Al₂O₃ between Ni₂Al₃ layers, but effects of aluminium oxides is relatively smaller for post-treated at 1150 °C, Ni₃Al layer can deform together with nickel layer like its single crystal by sliding, so it shows significantly strain-hardening and plastic flow as metal. Its mean strain and fracture strength at room temperature are about 13% and 786 MPa respectively.

KEYWORDS: nickel-nickel aluminide multilayer composites, thermal explosive synthesis, post-treatment

INTRODUCTION

Owing to their excellent high-temperature strength, chemical stability and low density, The aluminides of nickel as promising high-temperature structural materials are attracting the attention of many researchers. But their practical application was greatly restricted by their brittleness of room temperature, high sensitivity to composition and hard to shaping, and so on [1]. Recently, combustion synthesis(SHS) method has been applied to manufacture Ni-Al intermetallics [2,3]. However, combustion synthesis is difficult to fabricate full density products. So, J.C. Rawers attempts to produce metal intermetallics composites (MICs) by reaction sintering (hot-press SHS) of metal foils instead of metal powders [4]. The method for producing MICs has many advantages, such as: a) easily formatting full density products, b) conventionally fabricating near net shape composites through pre-deforming before reaction sintering, c) possibly obtaining well-bonded interfaces of metal and intermetallics, d) obtaining MICs of high fracture toughness, high-strength, high elastic modulus and light weight, and so on.

This paper mainly discusses the effects of microstructures, interfaces and aluminium oxide inclusions on tensile properties and behaviors in nickel-nickel aluminide multilayer composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Commercially pure Ni and Al foils degreased with acetone were cut into squares (80mm80mm) and stacked into laminations as shown in fig.1 in reference 4. The foil laminations in vacuum was heated to 620 °C for 1 hour under MPa pressure for thermal explosive synthesis, then heated to 750 °C, 950 °C, 1150 °C respectively for 4 hours under 5 MPa pressure for post-treatment. The tensile specimens were electro-discharger machined into flat dog-bone shaped bars. The effective gauge length and width was 20mm 10mm respectively, and the specimen thickness was 1mm. The tensile testing was taken in Instron at a constant crosshead speed of 1mm/min, correspondingly to strain rate of 8.3×10^{-4} /s in the gauge section. The microstructures and cross-sectional view of fractures were evaluated by JEOL probe in backscattered mode. Fracture surface was examined by SEM. Phases in composites were identified by x-ray energy-dispersive spectroscopy (XEDS) in SEM.

RESULTS

Microstructures

*Fig 1. Backscattered electron images of composites
 (a) reacted at 620 °C for 1h; (b) post-treated at 750 °C for 4h
 (c) post-treated at 950 °C for 4h; (d) post treated at 1150 °C for 4h*

The microstructure of composites by thermal explosive reacting Ni and Al foils at 620 °C for 1 hour under 1MPa pressure in vacuum consists of Ni and Ni₂Al₃ layer as shown in fig. 1 (a). Aluminium oxides coming from Al foil surfaces remain in the middle of Ni₂Al₃ layers.

The phases in composites post-treated at 750 °C, 950 °C and 1150 °C respectively for 4 hours under 5 MPa pressure are shown in fig.1 (b),(c) and (d) correspondingly. By post-treating 4 hours at 750 °C, thin layer of NiAl presents between Ni and Ni₂Al₃ layers. With increasing post-treating temperature to 950 °C, NiAl layer continually grows into Ni₂Al₃ layer and becomes thicker, and simultaneously Ni₃Al layer formats and grows by consuming Ni and NiAl. Aluminium oxides still remain between Ni₂Al₃ layers. After post-treated 4 hours at 1150 °C, Ni₂Al₃ layer was completely consumed, NiAl layer becomes thinner, and Ni₃Al layer grows thicker.

Tensile Properties and Behaviors

Table 1 gives the phases and room-temperature tensile properties of Ni-Ni aluminide multilayer composites post-treated at 750 °C, 950 °C and 1150 °C respectively, after reacted at 620 °C for 1h. The data in table 1 is average value of five specimens.

Table 1: Phases and tensile properties of Ni-Ni aluminide multilayer composites

post-treating temperature	phases	$\sigma_{0.2}$ (MPa)	σ_b (MPa)	δ (%)
750°C	Ni ₂ Al ₃ , NiAl, Ni	204	252	11.3
950°C	Ni ₂ Al ₃ , NiAl, Ni ₃ Al, Ni	83	98	0.51
1150°C	NiAl, Ni ₃ Al, Ni	348	786	12.8

Their typical room temperature tensile stress-strain curves are shown in fig 2.

Fig 2. Stress-strain curves of Ni-Ni aluminide multilayer composites.

DISCUSSIONS

Aluminium oxides coming from Al foil surfaces present in the middle of Ni_2Al_3 layers at primarily Al foils position before reacting. It indicates that Ni atoms are hard to diffuse through Al oxide films of Al foils and react with Al atoms, and only Al atoms are easy to diffuse through Al oxide films and format Ni_2Al_3 with Ni atoms.

*Fig 3. cross-sectional view of tensile fracture surface
(a) post-treated at 950°C for 4h; (b) post-treated at 1150°C for 4h*

*Fig 4. fracture surface of tensile specimens
(a) post-treated at 950°C for 1h; (b) post-treated at 1150°C for 4h*

After post-treated at 750°C poor-bonded interfaces between Ni₂Al₃ layers because of existence of Al oxide inclusions rapidly debond in the primary stage of tensile. Composites fail by bridging mechanism of cracks little by little. The sharp turns of curve 1 in fig 2. mean breaking of one or more Ni layers. so curve 1 wind sharply.

In composites post-treated at 950 °C, brittle Ni aluminides is relative thicker, and Ni layer is thinner, the microcracks in NiAl and Ni₂Al₃ layers are longer than others. and Ni₃Al is too thin to inhibit cracks propagating, so it's breaks at low stress level. Aluminium oxides like honeycomb can be viewed at the side of Ni₂Al₃ as shown at point A in fig 4.(a). Fracture surface in ductile Ni layer mainly consists of tearing prism and merely ductile voids. It indicates that cracks rapidly cross thorough Ni layer by tearing without significantly plastic deforming.

For post-treatment at 1150 °C, at the beginning of tension, NiAl layer can coordinately elastic deform with Ni₃Al and Ni layers, stress dispersion in Ni and Ni aluminides abides with combined rule. When stress is higher than the strength of NiAl, NiAl layers begin typically break by transgranular cleavage along its {110} due to intrinsic brittleness of NiAl. Cleavage planes cross mostly with tensile direction at about 45° angle, as shown in fig 3 (b) and at point A in fig 4 (b). Debonded interfaces of between NiAl layer with Al oxide inclusions seldom are viewed in fig 4(b). It suggests that effects of Al oxides is rather smaller at post-treatment at 1150 °C. The length of debonded interface of NiAl and Ni₃Al is very short, it suggests that interface of NiAl and Ni₃Al is strongly-bonded. The density of cleavage cracks in NiAl layers increases with increasing of tensile stress. The modulus of composites decreases little by little, so the slope of tensile curve at about 300 MPa becomes slow. However, cleavage cracks in NiAl layer are difficult to propagate through hard Ni₃Al layers, since merely cracks crossed through Ni layer are shown in fig 3(b). Ni₃Al layers inhibiting crack propagating in NiAl layers can retard the decrease of the effective area of composites, and strength continually increases by work hardening with strain increasing as shown in fig 2. And little debonded interface in the fracture surface shows that interface of Ni₃Al and Ni layer informed by reaction diffusion is strongly bonded too. The single Ni₃Al layer slides mainly in <110> {111} like single crystal and can cooperatively deform with Ni layer, many fine and intensive slipping lines can be clearly viewed in the side of Ni₃Al layer which debonded with NiAl layer as shown at point B in fig 4. Therefore the composites post-treated at 1150°C shows excellent plasticity and good strength. Significantly strain-hardening and plastic flow is presented under the tensile loading.

The slide deformation of Ni₃Al at 45° angle with tensile direction results in stress concentration at the interface of NiAl and Ni₃Al, and their well-bonded interface requires the deformation of NiAl with Ni₃Al layer together, therefore, the cleavage at about 45° angle with tensile direction are induced in NiAl layers.

CONCLUSIONS

- 1) Composites by reaction-synthesis of metal foil laminations and post-treatment at elevated temperature is a conventional and feasible method of producing material.
- 2) The good plasticity and strength can be made by reaction-synthesis at 620 °C for 1h under 1 MPa pressure and post-treated at 1150 °C for 4 hours under 5 MPa pressure in vacuum.

- 3) Ni atoms are hard to diffuse through Al oxide films of Al foils, and only Al atoms are easy to diffuse through Al oxide films and form Ni_2Al_3 with Ni atoms.
- 4) Al oxide inclusions on the aluminium foil surface result in the poor-bonded interface between intermetallics, especially for that post-treated at relative low temperature.
- 5) Generally, Ni_3Al layer is strongly bonded with Ni and NiAl layers.
- 6) The large deformation is attributed to the slide of Ni_3Al layer and cooperatively deformation of Ni_3Al and Ni layer together

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